

A Pre-Experimental Study to Assess the Effectiveness of Structured Teaching Programs (STP) on Knowledge Regarding Kwashiorkor and Marasmus Among Mothers of Under Five Year Children in Selected Rural Area of Bilaspur (C.G.)

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Abstract: Children are most vital populace for nations, for optimal psychological, physical and emotional growth for its perspective beneficial citizens. Populace below the age group of 5 years comprises 20 percent of total population and are the most high-risk segment for under nutritional disorders. The childhood is the vital phase of the life for laying the basement for optimal wellbeing and sound mind. Citizens of developing countries are the principal victims of under nutrition. Over 800 million children around the worldwide are encountered with under nutrition. More than half of the childhood deaths in growing nations are due the reason of under nutrition. Malnutrition covers a vast continuum of illness including malnutrition of protein calorie and alters the individual's growth on massive scale across the global. The most dispersed health and under nutrition problem in developing countries including India, is malnutrition of nutrition of calorie and growth retardation. United Nations International Children's Emergency Funds (UNICEF) document "The Progress for Children" identifies that in the growing world 146 million children underneath 5 years are below weight, predisposing them to serious problems from common childhood ailments. The normal developmental milestone in preschool children includes, naming colors, showing affection and hooping on one foot. The developmental mile stones assessed by how children play, learn, speak, behave and move. Preschool children try to investigate and explore the things surrounding them. Family plays important role in shaping personality of children by this age preschool child should be able to run tricycle, safety use of scissors, understand the sexuality difference, assist themselves to dress and undress, mingle with other children, sing a song and remind the story or part. **Problem Statement:** A Pre-Experimental Study to Assess the Effectiveness of Structured Teaching Programs (STP) on Knowledge Regarding Kwashiorkor and Marasmus Among Mothers of Under Five Year Children in Selected Rural Area of Bilaspur (C.G.). **Objectives of the Study:** 1) To assess the pre-test score on knowledge regarding kwashiorkor and marasmus among the mothers of under-five year children in the selected rural area of , Bilaspur (C.G.). 2) To assess the post test level of knowledge

regarding kwashiorkor and marasmus under five-year children in selected rural area of Bilaspur (C.G.). 3) To evaluate the effectiveness of structured teaching programme in terms of knowledge regarding kwashiorkor and marasmus among the mothers of under-five year children in the selected rural area of, Bilaspur (C.G.). 4) To find out the association between pre test knowledge score regarding kwashiorkor and marasmus mother of under five-year children with their selected sociodemographic variable. **Hypothesis:** To examine the following hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance: H1: There will be a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test knowledge scores of among mothers of under-five year children. H2: There will be a significant association between knowledge score and selected demographic variables. **Research Design:** Pre experimental design. (i.e.) one group pre test and post test design was used to accomplish the objective of the study. **Setting:** The study was conducted in the rural area Pandhi (Anganwadi), Bilaspur. **Sample:** Sample are Selected by Purposive Sampling Techniques technique was used for the selection of patients. The counts of 60 samples were selected for the study.

Keywords: Structured Teaching Programs, Kwashiorkor, Marasmus.

1. Introduction

Today's healthy child is tomorrow's better citizen. The development of a healthy child is influenced by many factors. Under-five children form the most vulnerable group of children who are prone to many infective diseases and nutritional deficiencies.

Children are the future pillars of a nation. The nutrition of these children would determine the strength of tomorrow's nation. Inadequate nutrition of these children leads to retarded growth and development and may cripple the child for life. In a developing country like India, there are many constraints to

better living and adequate nutrition, lack of awareness about the dietary requirements and nutritive value of different food are the main causes of prevailing malnutrition among preschool children.

Children under the age of five years are the hardest on a global scale. The five nutritional deficiency diseases that are being accorded the highest priority action are kwashiorkor, marasmus, xerophthalmia, nutritional anemia, and endemic goitre. Malnutrition is preventable when tried well in advance; improving mother's educational levels and providing mothers with the information that they need on children care are the important components of a strategy to improve nutrition.

Good health is the basic aim of any development effort. The concept of human development rests on three pillars: knowledge, health and livelihood. Health of the people has been recognized as a valuable national resource and the government's endeavor has been to improve the same and enable them to give to enhance the nation's productivity. Health defined by World Health Organization (WHO) as a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being and not merely to an absence of any diseases or infirmity. Physical health implies the perfect functioning of the body (WHO).

2. Methods

A pre-experimental one group pre-test, post-test research design was utilizing to assess the effectiveness of structured teaching programme regarding kwashiorkor and marasmus among mothers of under five-year children in selected rural area of Bilaspur (C.G.)."

Where the subject was selected by purposive sampling techniques. An extensive review of literature was undertaken various related concepts. The study adopted the Nola Penders health promotion model theory based on personal and interpersonal systems including perception, judgement, action, reaction, interaction and transaction. Purposive Sampling techniques were used to obtain 60 samples. The tool was self-structured teaching programme.

3. Results

Results show that the pre-test score 59 (98.33%) belong to poor, 1 (1.66%) belong to average, 0 (0%) are belongs to good. in post-test majority of them i.e., 16 (26.66%) belong to poor, 43 (71.66%) are belong to average, 1 (1.66%) belongs to good.

4. Findings

The assessment of overall analysis of knowledge level of kwashiorkor and marasmus pre test were 59 (98.3%) of the samples had average knowledge, 1 (1.7%) had below average knowledge and good were 0 (0%) while in post test 1 (1.66%) had good knowledge, 43 (71.6%) had average knowledge on the Z value of structured teaching program was 12.76 which is highly significant at 0.05 which proves the effectiveness of the structured teaching program. Hence H1 was accepted. There is significant association between pre test knowledge with selected socio demographic variables (area of residence,

duration of illness, any associated illness, if yes than disease condition) at the level of 0.05 significance. Hence H2 was accepted.

5. Conclusion

The study concluded that the structure teaching programme was effective in increasing the knowledge regarding kwashiorkor and marasmus mother of under five-year children.

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